

THE EFFECT OF COMMUNICATION STYLES OF SCHOOL HEADS ON COMMUNICATION SATISFACTION AMONG TEACHERS

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Abstract

This study described the school heads' extent of use of aggressive communication style, assertive communication style, open communication style, and inclusive communication style. This study also describes the teachers' communication satisfaction along personal feedback, supervisor communication, horizontal communication, organizational integration, organizational perspective, communication climate, and media quality. Descriptive-correlational methods of research were used in this study. The primary tool of data collection was a questionnaire which was given to five hundred seven (507) teachers. It was found that the school heads did not use aggressive communication style, used assertive communication style to a high extent, and also used open and inclusive communication styles to a very high extent. The teachers were much satisfied with the aspects of communication in their respective schools. This study also revealed that there was a significant difference in the school heads' communication style when analyzed according to age, length of service as a school head, and number of seminars/training attended in organizational communication. The school heads used several communication styles to effectively lead their teachers. They used aggressive communication style to a very slight extent and assertive communication style to a high extent. The school heads applied the open communication style and inclusive

communication style to a very high extent. The teachers were much satisfied with the way their school heads communicate in leading them. It can be inferred that the school heads' communication styles used highly affects the teachers' communication satisfaction in all aspects of communication.

Keywords: *Aggressive Communication Style; Assertive Communication Style; Open Communication Style; Inclusive Communication Style; Teachers' Communication Satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

Communication bridges the gap between individuals and groups through flow of information and understandings between them. Information is the most vital aspect for communication. It is the information which is transmitted, studied, analyzed and interpreted and stored. The school manager therefore has to spare time to collect, analyze and store information for decision-making and routine day to day activity. As an essential thing in organization, communication serves two essential functions. First, it disseminates the information needed by employees to get things done and build relationship of trust and commitment. Second, it also helps to build relationship and facilitates achievement of goals. People working the organization must be informed not only about the work assigned to them but communicate everything in the organization. It is central to organizational success and multidimensional. It is widely accepted idea that no organization without communication. Leaders use the majority of their time communicating in different forms, face to face meeting discussion, letters, and electronic mail. In any organization, communication is a necessity for coordinating most activities, and this is especially true in educational institutions. Given the widespread changes in education today, educational institution need effective leaders who are good communicators Ibrahim & Mahmoud (2017).

Communication styles when adopted, it implies certain things about personality, mood, and even the type of conversation that will transpire. It is important to note that while people usually speak with one of these communication styles, they don't always stick the same one. Depending on the speaker's mode or desired effect, their communication style might change from time to time, dropping jaws and raising eyebrows. Communication style is very important in managerial work. Sherman (2015) identified 4 communication styles namely: inclusive communication, open communication, aggressive communication, and assertive communication. An inclusive communication style is a style that school leaders ensure that all staff members in the school feel free to get involved in decisions that affect their day –to-day activities, Barlund, (2008). Akinwale & Okotoni, (2018) described open communication styles as a style of communication in which the leader consciously creates an atmosphere where all individuals within organization express their views and opinion on issues affecting the running of the organization. Assertive communication styles is a practice of communication that able to stand up for your own or other peoples' right in a calm and positive way without being aggressive or passively accepting wrong. Lastly, aggressive communication style which explained as individuals express their feelings and opinions and advocate for their needs in a way that violates the rights of others.

Furthermore, attainment of collective goals in all organizations involves good communication styles by school leaders. All organizations envisioned a good working atmosphere between managers and workers through suitable communication styles because it is a road for an organization to thrive. It was also believed that an effective school administrator is expected to have an excellent communication styles and practices that will fuel communication satisfaction among teachers. Akinwale and Okotoni, (2018) explained that communication system in school and other organizations can be likened to blood in human beings. No administrative functions can be carried out in schools without good and effective communication. Secondary school principals plan, organize, control, coordinate and perform other related administrative functions through communication. Okotoni, Akinwale & Ayotunde, (2019) emphasized that in a school system, communication took place between and among principals, teaching and non-teaching staff, students as well as other stakeholders.

Although several researches have explored the significant impact of communication styles of school heads on their teachers' morale, satisfaction, etc, there is a scarce study on how the school heads' communication styles affect the communication satisfaction of teachers. This research gap limits our understanding of how effective communication strategies, school heads can enhance teachers' communication satisfaction, leading to a more positive and productive work environment. Ibrahim & Mahmud, (2017) stressed that in schools, communication happens at all times and in many ways. However, principals have certain communication styles, or patterns when sharing their ideas and thoughts and these styles or patterns to a great extent could determine the teachers' communication satisfaction within a school system.

However, in some cases, particularly in the school environment of most schools in the first congressional district of the division of Zamboanga del Norte, as a specific social environment, it is assumed that communication within school is both directly and indirectly affected by many factors. Among them, is the school heads communication practices. There are some practices of school heads in terms of communication that has been outdated and prone of increasing conflict. It can absolutely fires up communication dissatisfaction among teachers. Conflict usually arises because teachers cannot adapt this old practices and get tired of it. They will go against it that could make them uncooperative to schools heads plans for the school's improvement. Their work performance is greatly affected because of their communication dissatisfaction. Another is the communication culture, sometimes it came out to be chaotic. Communication styles between teachers and school heads as well, just like communication practices of school heads, some of its communication styles could also developed informal networks, and this grapevine usually becomes a root cause of miscommunication among teachers and school heads. This actually hampers implementation of school programs, projects, and activities. Whenever obstruction had been developed within the work environment or school environment, employees' or teachers' communication satisfaction depletes, so then, it will shake the working relationship between school managers and subordinates and definitely achievement of school goals will be immensely affected.

Therefore, with this above-mentioned situation, the researcher believed that it is timely and relevant to pursue this study to provide data with regards to the effect of school heads' communication styles on teachers' communication satisfaction within the first congressional district, division of Zamboanga del Norte.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to describe the communication styles used by school heads and the teachers' communication satisfaction. This also determined the effect of communication styles used by school heads on the teachers' communication satisfaction.

Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What are the communication styles used by school heads and to what extent?
2. What is the level of teachers' communication satisfaction?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of use of communication styles of school heads and the level of teachers' communication satisfaction?

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey and correlational methods of research using a questionnaire as the primary tool of data collection. Descriptive analysis was used to describe the communication styles employed by school heads and the teachers' communication satisfaction. Correlational analysis was used to establish the relationships between the independent and dependent variables.

This study used five hundred seven (507) classroom teachers who were randomly selected from the twenty-two (22) schools of the first congressional district, schools division of Zamboanga del Norte.

The questionnaire used to know the communication styles of school heads was adapted from the study of De Vries et al., (2009) which measured through aggressive, assertive, open, and inclusive communication styles. This used the Likert scale rating from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The teachers' communication satisfaction was measured through: personal feedback, supervisor communication, horizontal communication, organizational integration, organizational perspective, communication climate, and media quality. Communication Satisfaction Questionnaire (CSQ) developed by Downs and Hazen (1977) was used to evaluate communication satisfaction of teachers using a Likert scale rating from 1 (Poor) to 5 (Excellent). The questionnaires were pre-tested to non-respondents to get the reliability and validity. The reliability and validity of the instruments were found high.

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the data collected for this study:

Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to describe the extent of use of school heads' communication styles and teachers' communication satisfaction.

Spearman-Rank Correlation Coefficient was used to test the relationship between school heads' communication styles and teachers' communication satisfaction.

The data were analyzed using MS Excel and Jamovi v. 2.3.19. The relationship was tested using a .05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The Extent of Use of Aggressive Communication Style by School Heads is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The Extent of Use of Aggressive Communication Style by School Heads

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Level/Interpretation
1. Use of threats to motivate teacher's to work	1.51	.894	Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent
2. Use of obscene language when relating with teachers	1.47	.878	Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent
3. Easily find faults in whatever teacher do	1.56	.946	Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent
4. Display of anger when displeases by teacher's actions	1.66	.932	Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent
5. Transfer of aggression when things are not happening as expected	1.56	.832	Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent
6. Dislike being confronted by teachers in general meeting	1.62	.872	Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent
7. Use query and derogatory words when teachers make mistakes on the job	1.50	.886	Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent
Grand Weighted Mean	1.55	.894	Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent		1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ To a slight extent
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree/To a moderate extent		3.41 – 4.20 Agree/To a high extent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent		

The Extent of Use of Assertive Communication Style by School Heads is shown in Table 2.

Table 2

The Extent of Use of Assertive Communication Style by School Heads

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Level/Interpretation
1. Fluency in the clarification of ideas	4.11	.768	Agree/To a high extent
2. Clearly express a chain of thought during argument of a point	4.09	.804	Agree/To a high extent

3. Taking the lead in a conversation in the school	4.19	.777	Agree/To a high extent
4. Standing for the rights in school when necessary	4.22	.748	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
5. Determines the direction of conversation in a meeting	4.19	.740	Agree/To a high extent
6. Giving concise and unambiguous messages to teachers	4.02	.830	Agree/To a high extent
7. Respecting the rights and dignity of teachers in the school	4.33	.812	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
Grand Weighted Mean	4.16	.788	Agree/To a high extent
1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent			1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ To a slight extent
2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree/To a moderate extent			3.41 – 4.20 Agree/To a high extent
4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree/To a very high extent			

The Extent of Use of Open Communication Style by School Heads is shown in Table 3.

Table 3

The Extent of Use of Open Communication Style by School Heads

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Level/Interpretation
1. Talk freely with all the teachers	4.43	.687	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
2. Teachers are allowed to freely express themselves in meetings	4.41	.733	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
3. Teachers feel free to discuss challenges facing them in teaching	4.40	.707	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
4. Encourage teachers even when students are not performing as expected	4.37	.737	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
5. Encourage teachers to give feedback on policies and programs of school	4.38	.756	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
6. Showing of concern to teachers challenges in a professional way	4.28	.761	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
7. Often show a lot of understanding for other people's problem	4.28	.805	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
Grand Weighted Mean	4.36	.743	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent			1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ To a slight extent
2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree/To a moderate extent			3.41 – 4.20 Agree/To a high extent
4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree/To a very high extent			

The Extent of Use of Inclusive Communication Style by School Heads is shown in Table 4.

Table 4

The Extent of Use of Inclusive Communication Style by School Heads

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Level/Interpretation
1. Making opinions counts in day-to-day decision that affect teacher's work	4.22	.762	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
2. Inclusion of one or more teachers in the school management	4.26	.749	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
3. Principal seeks for teacher's idea and inputs in the school programs	4.31	.762	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
4. Showing of admiration for teachers' work	4.31	.761	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
5. Teachers are allowed to participate in the planning of school work/policy	4.29	.758	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
6. Staff are made to be aware and have understanding of all school procedures and policies	4.32	.761	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
7. Making the school environment comfortable for all the teachers	4.36	.764	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
Grand Weighted Mean	4.30	.760	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/To a very slight extent			1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ To a slight extent
2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree/To a moderate extent			3.41 – 4.20 Agree/To a high extent
4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree/To a very high extent			

The Summary of the Extent of Use of Communication Style by School Heads is shown in Table 5.

Table 5

The Summary of the Extent of Use of Communication Style by School Heads

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Level /Interpretation
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Aggressive Communication	1.55	.894	Strongly Disagree/Not at all
Assertive Communication	4.16	.788	Agree/To a high extent
Open Communication	4.36	.743	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
Inclusive Communication	4.30	.760	Strongly Agree/To a very high extent
1.00 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree/Not at all		1.81 – 2.60 Disagree/ To a slight extent	
2.61 – 3.40 Neither/To a moderate extent		3.41 – 4.20 Agree/To a high extent	
4.21 – 5.00 Strongly Agree/To a very high extent			

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Personal Feedback of Teachers is shown in Table 6.

Table 6

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Personal Feedback of Teachers

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description/Interpretation
1. Information about how my job compares with others	3.83	.785	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
2. Information about how I am being judged	3.79	.810	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
3. Recognition of my efforts	3.89	.744	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
4. Reports on how problems in my job are handled	3.90	.733	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
5. Extent to which superiors know and understand the problems faced by subordinates	3.92	.718	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Grand Weighted Mean	3.87	.760	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
1.00 – 1.80 Poor/Not Satisfied		1.81 – 2.60 Fair/Slightly Satisfied	
2.61 – 3.40 Satisfactory/Moderately Satisfied		3.41 – 4.20 Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied	
4.21 – 5.00 Excellent/Very Much Satisfied			

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Supervisor Communication of Teachers is shown in Table 7.

Table 7*The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Supervisor Communication of Teachers*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description/Interpretation
1. Extent to which my supervisor listens and pays attention to me	3.98	.717	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
2. Extent to which my supervisor offers guidance for solving job related problems	3.96	.744	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
3. Extent to which my supervisor trust me	4.01	.710	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
4. Extent to which my supervisor is open to ideas	3.98	.719	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
5. Extent to which the amount of supervision given to me is about right	3.94	.738	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Grand Weighted Mean	3.97	.726	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
1.00 – 1.80 Poor/Not Satisfied		1.81 – 2.60 Fair/Slightly Satisfied	
2.61 – 3.40 Satisfactory/Moderately Satisfied		3.41 – 4.20 Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied	
4.21 – 5.00 Excellent/Very Much Satisfied			

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Horizontal Communication of Teachers is shown in Table 8.

Table 8*The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Horizontal Communication of Teachers*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description/Interpretation
1. Extent to which the grapevine is active in our organization	3.76	.810	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
2. Extent to which horizontal communication with other employees is accurate and free flowing	3.90	.703	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
3. Extent to which communication practices are adaptable to emergencies	3.93	.712	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
4. Extent to which my work group is compatible	3.95	.701	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
5. Extent to which informal communication is active and accurate	3.88	.763	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied

Grand Weighted Mean	3.88	.741	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
1.00 – 1.80 Poor/Not Satisfied			1.81 – 2.60 Fair/Slightly Satisfied
2.61 – 3.40 Satisfactory/Moderately Satisfied			3.41 – 4.20 Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
4.21 – 5.00 Excellent/Very Much Satisfied			

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Organizational Integration of Teachers is shown in Table 9.

Table 9

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Organizational Integration of Teachers

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description/Interpretation
1. Information about the progress of my job	3.97	.696	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
2. Personal news	3.89	.707	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
3. Information about departmental policies and goals	4.02	.687	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
4. Information about the requirements of my job	4.04	.719	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
5. Information about benefits and pay	4.02	.735	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Grand Weighted Mean	3.99	.710	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
1.00 – 1.80 Poor/Not Satisfied			1.81 – 2.60 Fair/Slightly Satisfied
2.61 – 3.40 Satisfactory/Moderately Satisfied			3.41 – 4.20 Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
4.21 – 5.00 Excellent/Very Much Satisfied			

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Organizational Perspective of Teachers is shown in Table 10.

Table 10

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Organizational Perspective of Teachers

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description/Interpretation
1. Information about companies policies and goals	4.02	.710	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
2. Information about our organization's financial standing	3.89	.758	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied

3. Information about changes in our organization	3.94	.677	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
4. Information about government action affecting my company	3.94	.699	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
5. Information about accomplishments and/or failures of the organization	3.95	.680	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Grand Weighted Mean	3.95	.706	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
1.00 – 1.80 Poor/Not Satisfied		1.81 – 2.60 Fair/Slightly Satisfied	
2.61 – 3.40 Satisfactory/Moderately Satisfied		3.41 – 4.20 Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied	
4.21 – 5.00 Excellent/Very Much Satisfied			

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Communication Climate of Teachers is shown in Table 11.

Table 11

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Communication Climate of Teachers

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description/Interpretation
1. Extent to which the organization's communication motivates and stimulates an enthusiasm for meeting its goals	4.06	2.267	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
2. Extent to which the people in my organization have great ability as communicators	3.95	.725	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
3. Extent to which the organization's communication makes me identify with it or feel a vital part of it	3.94	.722	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
4. Extent to which I receive in time the information needed to do my job	3.95	.715	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
5. Extent to which conflicts are handled appropriately through proper communication channels	3.98	.712	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Grand Weighted Mean	3.98	1.200	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
1.00 – 1.80 Poor/Not Satisfied		1.81 – 2.60 Fair/Slightly Satisfied	
2.61 – 3.40 Satisfactory/Moderately Satisfied		3.41 – 4.20 Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied	
4.21 – 5.00 Excellent/Very Much Satisfied			

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Media Quality of Teachers is shown in Table 12.

Table 12

The Level of Communication Satisfaction along Media Quality of Teachers

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description/Interpretation
1. Extent to which my company's publications are interesting and helpful	3.92	.650	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
2. Extent to which our meetings are well organized	3.93	.703	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
3. Extent to which written directives and reports are clear and concise	3.92	.721	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
4. Extent to which the attitudes toward communication in the organization are basically healthy	3.92	.693	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
5. Extent to which the amount of communication in the organization is about right	3.91	.732	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Grand Weighted Mean	3.92	.700	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
1.00 – 1.80 Poor/Not Satisfied		1.81 – 2.60 Fair/Slightly Satisfied	
2.61 – 3.40 Satisfactory/Moderately Satisfied		3.41 – 4.20 Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied	
4.21 – 5.00 Excellent/Very Much Satisfied			

The Summary of the Level of Communication Satisfaction of Teachers is shown in Table 13.

Table 13

The Summary of the Level of Communication Satisfaction of Teachers

Aspect of Communication	GWM	Standard Deviation	Description/Interpretation
Personal Feedback	3.87	.760	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Supervisor Communication	3.97	.726	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Horizontal Communication	3.88	.741	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Organizational Integration	3.99	.710	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Organizational Perspective	3.95	.706	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied

Communication Climate	3.98	1.200	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Media Quality	3.92	.700	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
Overall Weighted Mean	3.94	.810	Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied
1.00 – 1.80 Poor/Not Satisfied		1.81 – 2.60 Fair/Slightly Satisfied	
2.61 – 3.40 Satisfactory/Moderately Satisfied		3.41 – 4.20 Very Satisfactory/Much Satisfied	
4.21 – 5.00 Excellent/Very Much Satisfied			

The Relationship Between the Extent of Use of Communication Styles of School Heads and Level of Communication Satisfaction of Teachers is shown in Table 14.

Table 14

The Relationship Between the Extent of Use of Communication Styles of School Heads and Level of Communication Satisfaction of Teachers

Variables	Computed ρ	P-Value	Interpretation
Aggressive Communication Style and Communication Satisfaction	-.379	.000	Medium/Moderate Negative Correlation/ Significant
Assertive Communication Style and Communication Satisfaction	.354	.000	Medium/Moderate Positive Correlation/ Significant
Open Communication Style and Communication Satisfaction	.486	.000	Medium/Moderate Positive Correlation/ Significant
Inclusive Communication Style and Communication Satisfaction	.591	.000	Large/High Positive Correlation/ Significant

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the extent of use of aggressive communication style of school heads. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, level of agreement, and interpretation. The teachers strongly disagree that their school heads use threats in motivating them. They find their school heads as modest and cannot be easily irritated. They also found that their school heads were open to suggestions and accommodating in dealing with them. The collective rating of the teachers through the grand weighted mean 1.55 and standard deviation .894 indicated that the school heads used aggressive communication style to a very slight extent. Aggressive communication styles of school heads are generally not effective in promoting a positive and healthy learning environment. Aggression can create fear, anxiety, and a

hostile atmosphere among students, teachers, and staff. It can also hinder effective communication and collaboration, which are essential for a successful educational institution. The result of this study is consistent to the findings of Thompson (2020) that shed light on the negative consequences of aggressive communication, such as increased stress, decreased job satisfaction, and reduced commitment to the school.

Table 2 presents the extent of use of assertive communication style of school heads. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, level of agreement, and interpretation. The teachers strongly agree that their school heads stood for the rights in their school and respect the rights and dignity of teachers. The teachers agree that their school heads were fluent and clear in giving them instructions. The school heads ensured that the messages were clear as they provide directions so not to confuse the teachers. The grand weighted mean 4.16 and standard deviation .788 indicate, in general, that the school heads used assertive communication style to a high extent. The result corroborated to the findings of Mohamed & Abidin (2021) as it revealed that most of the dominant communication styles practiced by the principals at vocational colleges in Selangor was assertive communication style. The results also showed that the level of school culture at vocational colleges in Selangor was high based on three factors which are shared leadership and vision, collegial teaching and learning, and professional commitment. The assertive communication style of school heads highlighted the importance of effective communication in educational leadership. By understanding the components, benefits, challenges, and strategies for developing assertive communication skills, school leaders can enhance their ability to lead and manage their schools successfully.

Table 3 presents the extent of use of open communication style of school heads. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, level of agreement, and interpretation. As reflected in the table, the teachers perceived that their school heads effectively lead their respective schools as they encourage an open communication in providing instructions. Their school heads and teachers share the necessary information for the completion of the assigned tasks. This allows the teachers to get more engaged to work effectively to achieve school success. The grand weighted mean 4.36 with standard deviation .743 indicate, in general, that the school heads used open communication style to a very high extent. The study of Samuel and C.A (2018) Assessment of Principals' Communication Styles and Administrative Impact on Secondary Schools in Osun State, Nigeria supports the present findings which showed that this kind of communication style was adopted by school heads respected the opinions of the teachers. Principals allowed teachers to take active part in the decision making in schools, They made teachers aware of what they were meant to do precisely and ambiguously. Above all they protected their rights and respected the rights of others as well. An open communication style can be highly effective in promoting a positive and productive school environment as it helps to build trust between school heads, teachers, students, and parents, fosters collaboration and teamwork among all stakeholders, create opportunities for sharing ideas, feedback, and suggestions, leading to better decision-making and problem-solving, and boost morale and motivation among teachers and students.

Table 4 presents the extent of use of inclusive communication style of school heads. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, level of agreement, and interpretation. It can be seen in the table that the teachers perceived that they were highly valued in school. Their school heads share information in a way that all teachers can understand. The school heads also made the school environment that is respectful and inclusive of all and enabled the teachers to contribute diverse perspectives to make them feel they belong to the school. The grand weighted mean 4.30 and standard deviation .760 indicate, in general, that the school heads used inclusive communication style to a very high extent. This result corroborated the findings of Samuel and Okotoni (2018). Their study on assessment of principals' communication styles and administrative impact on secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria showed that the highest percentage of communication style used by the principals in the secondary schools in Osun State was the inclusive communication style as 69% of the respondents gave this response. The data indicated that inclusive communication style is the most common communication style used by school heads in Osun, Nigeria. An inclusive communication style of school heads is highly effective in promoting a positive and inclusive school environment as it ensured that all members of the school community feel valued and included, recognizes and celebrates the diversity within the school community, and encourage dialogue and active listening, which helps to build bridges of understanding and promote empathy towards different perspectives and experiences.

Table 5 presents the summary of the extent of use of communication styles by school heads. The collective rating of the teachers through the grand weighted mean 1.55 and standard deviation .894 indicated that the school heads used aggressive communication style to a very slight extent. The grand weighted mean 4.16 and standard deviation .788 indicate, in general, that the school heads used assertive communication style to a high extent. The grand weighted mean 4.36 with standard deviation .743 indicate, in general, that the school heads used open communication style to a very high extent. The grand weighted mean 4.30 and standard deviation .760 indicate, in general, that the school heads used inclusive communication style to a very high extent.

Table 6 presents the level of communication satisfaction along personal feedback of teachers. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, description, and interpretation. The table depicts that the personal feedback received by teachers from the school heads were very satisfactory. The teachers learn something positive from the positive suggestions of their school heads. The teachers received appreciation and recognition for a job well done. The school heads were able to provide coaching whenever the teachers were faced with problems at work. The grand weighted mean of 3.87 with standard deviation .760, in general, indicated that the teachers were much satisfied of the way their school heads provide them feedbacks. The research of Terek, et. al (2015) is supported by the findings of this study. It was revealed that on their educational research on the impact of leadership on the communication satisfaction of primary school teachers in Serbia, it confirms that from the dimensions of communication satisfaction, CS4, Personal Feedback, had the strongest

correlation. If teachers are satisfied with leadership then, they are satisfied with the feedback they receive from the principal in order to resolve their problems adequately.

Table 7 presents the level of communication satisfaction along supervisor communication of teachers. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, description, and interpretation. The teachers were much satisfied on how their school heads listened and paid attention to their concern and offered them guidance to deal with problems. They were also much satisfied to the trust and the amount of supervision given to them by their school heads. The grand weighted mean 3.97 with standard deviation .726, in general, indicated that they were much satisfied on how their school heads communicate their ideas and expectations more clearly and convincingly. This corroborated findings of the study of Shamsul Alam (2016) the respondents are satisfied with the extent to which their supervisor offers guidance for solving the job related problems.

Table 8 presents the level of communication satisfaction along horizontal communication of teachers. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, description, and interpretation. The teachers were much satisfied with the flow of messages among teachers in the school. The teachers believed that the flow of accurate information provided them with positive feedback that increased the cooperation and efficiency between them. Horizontal communication in school positively enhanced the teachers' morale and satisfaction. The grand weighted mean 3.88 with standard deviation .741, in general, indicated that the teachers were much satisfied with the effective use of horizontal communication. The present study supported the findings of Jamail et al. (2019) on her study of Gen-Y teachers leadership on conflict management and communication satisfaction wherein the results stipulates that the highest mean score for communication satisfaction was on the dimension of horizontal communication with 3.91. Generation Y teachers feel comfortable with informal communication through grapevine network because this generation of teachers does not have any problem engaging in groups.

Table 9 presents the level of communication satisfaction along organizational integration of teachers. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, description, and interpretation. The teachers were much satisfied as they were informed about the policies and goals of the school. The school heads provided necessary feedbacks about the job requirement of teachers and their progress. The teachers were also informed about their benefits and pay. The grand weighted mean 3.99 with standard deviation .710, in general, indicated that the teachers were much satisfied on how their school heads demonstrate the ability to lead them. The study of Shamsul Alam (2016) on Communication Satisfaction: A study on Junior Executives working in Private Sector of Bangladesh supports the present findings. Based on the result, in organizational integration dimension, majority of the respondents (52.1%) are found to be satisfied with due information they receive about their progress in their job.

Table 10 presents the level of communication satisfaction along organizational perspective of teachers. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard

deviation, grand weighted mean, description, and interpretation. The teachers were much satisfied on how they were informed about DepEd goals and policies and financial standing of the school. They were also informed when there are changes in the organization including the accomplishments and failures of the school. The grand weighted mean 3.95 with standard deviation .706, in general, indicated that the teachers were much satisfied with the way the school heads define their roles and responsibility within the school. The study of Sharma, Lampley, & Good (2015) on organizational communication: perceptions of staff members' level of communication satisfaction and job satisfaction support the present findings. It showed that the 95% confidence interval for the mean score on the communication satisfaction organizational perspective dimension ranged from 0.78 to 1.05. the effect size ($d=0.67$) indicate a medium effect. The results indicated that participants were generally somewhat satisfied with organizational perspective.

Table 11 presents the level of communication satisfaction along communication climate of teachers. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, description, and interpretation. The teachers were much satisfied on how their school heads motivated and stimulated their enthusiasm to meet the school's goals. The teachers received in time the information needed to do their jobs. They were also much satisfied on how their school heads handled conflicts appropriately through proper communication channels. The grand weighted mean 3.98 with standard deviation 1.200, in general, indicated that the teachers were much satisfied the communication climate in their schools. The study of Jahn (2019) on school climate and communication satisfaction corroborates the present findings wherein according to the data, the mean score for communication climate is $M=4.65$, $SD=1.08$, $n=47$ this indicate that teachers are mostly satisfied with communication climate.

Table 12 presents the level of communication satisfaction along media quality of teachers. The table shows the indicators, weighted mean, standard deviation, grand weighted mean, description, and interpretation. The teachers were much satisfied with the quality of school publications. They were also much satisfied on how meetings were organized and that the directives and reports were clear and concise. The teachers have good attitude toward communication in school. The amount of communication in the organization was just about right. The grand weighted mean 3.92 with standard deviation .700, in general, indicated that the teachers were much satisfied on communication along media quality. The educational research of Sharma et al. (2015) on organizational communication - perception of staff members' level of communication satisfaction and job satisfaction corroborates this findings. Results found out that staff members perceived their level of satisfaction on media quality dimension as somewhat satisfied. A strong positive relationship of communication styles practiced in the organization and communication satisfaction.

Table 13 presents the summary of the level of communication satisfaction of teachers. The table shows the aspect of communication, grand weighted mean (GWM), standard deviation, overall weighted mean, description, and interpretation. The grand weighted means indicate that teachers were much satisfied with the personal feedback,

supervisor communication, horizontal, communication, organizational integration, organizational perspective, communication climate, and media quality. The collective rating of the teachers obtained an overall weighted mean 3.94 with standard deviation .810 which indicated that the teachers were much satisfied with the aspects of communication in their respective schools. The present findings are supported by the study of Jahn (2019) about teacher's performance of organizational school climate and communication satisfaction, which found out that teachers are mostly satisfied with the communication in these areas. Based on the mean scores, teachers had the highest level of communication for media quality. Media quality refers to meetings, written communication and the extent to which the total amount of communication in the organization is adequate. Others areas of communication such as horizontal and informal, organizational integration got also a high satisfaction result except corporate information and personal feedback which have less score but not well below the conceptual midpoint which could not be thought of as weakness.

Table 14 presents the relationship between the extent of use of communication styles of school heads and level of communication satisfaction of teachers. The table shows the variables, computed ρ , P-value, and interpretation. The computed rho ρ values -.379 for 'Aggressive Communication Style and Communication Satisfaction', .354 for 'Assertive Communication Style and Communication Satisfaction', .486 for 'Open Communication Style and Communication Satisfaction', and .591 for 'Inclusive Communication Style and Communication Satisfaction' produced P-values that are less than 0.05 level of significance. This means that there was a significant relationship between the extent of use of communication styles of school heads and level of communication satisfaction of teachers. This implies that the communication styles used by school heads significantly affects the communication satisfaction of teachers. This result corroborated the study of De la Torre (2016). The results of the correlational analysis between Millennial communication styles, as determined by the MCSS, and their communication satisfaction with their supervisors, as determined by the ICSI, showed that Millennials characterized as either Drivers or Analyticals were significantly satisfied with the communication skills of their supervisors.

Wikaningrum et al. (2018) study on the relationship among leadership styles, communication skills, and employees satisfaction: A study on equal employment opportunity in leadership supports the present findings wherein in the hypothesis 1a testing using regression analysis showed that the leaders' communication ability had a positive and significant effect on the employees' communication satisfaction ($b = 0.766; p=0,000$). Therefore, it is proven that the hypothesis was supported. It could be understood if the communication skills affected the employees' satisfaction on the communication with the direct leaders. It is because leaders cannot be separated from their roles as communicators. Submission of instructions, information, duties and responsibilities of employees absolutely covers clarity on all things which did not only benefit the organization, but also the employees. So when a leader can be an effective information conveyor, a good listener, and sensitive to the needs and aspirations of the bottom, the employees who are under his/her command will be more satisfied with the communication needs.

Conclusions

The school heads used several communication styles to effectively lead their teachers. They used aggressive communication style to a very slight extent and assertive communication style to a high extent. The school heads applied the open communication style and inclusive communication style to a very high extent. The teachers were much satisfied with the way their school heads communicate in leading them. It can be inferred that the school heads' communication styles used highly affects the teachers' communication satisfaction in all aspects of communication.

Recommendations

After a thorough examination of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are given to enhance effective leadership communication of secondary school heads in the division of Zamboanga del Norte:

1. School heads of the division of Zamboanga del Norte must adopt and implement this newly proposed interactive model of communication to achieve a high level of communication satisfaction among teaching and non-teaching personnel in their learning institutions.
2. The top-level management of the schools division of Zamboanga del Norte should organize, conduct seminars/trainings on organizational communication to enhance more of the principal's communication skills for effective school leadership communication.
3. School administrators in the first congressional district of the division of Zamboanga del Norte should sustain the current communication satisfaction of teachers through a constant adaptation of inclusive communication style, open communication style, and assertive communication style.
4. Teachers must practice proper feed backing as an upward communication practices to give off accurate responses needed by the school heads in doing his or her job as managers of the educational environment.
5. Other researchers must look into same variables in broader perspective to validate results of this investigation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors have stated that they have no potential conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. The authors accomplished this study in compliance with the research ethics protocol. Informed consent were given to the respondents before the research instrument was distributed. The data were treated with utmost confidentiality.

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